

ReNEW

D5.5 Exploitation and Commercialisation Strategy & Plan v1

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
EU	European
GA	Grand Agreement
GRIWT	Green Resilient Inland Water Transport
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IWT	Inland Water Transport
JEA	Joint Exploitation Agreement
KER	Key Exploitable Result
R&I	Research&Innovation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WS	Workshop

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1 Executive Summary

Within this report, the ReNEW exploitation planning is unveiled, serving as an all-encompassing framework connecting various project components such as dissemination, stakeholder analysis, technology outlook, economic analysis, and the business plan. Exploitation tasks are set to start in the current months, with a primary focus on identifying KERs and defining their commercial potential. Concurrently, insights from stakeholder analysis, technology trends, and market analysis will shape the exploitation strategy.

The uptake of the ReNEW outcomes will be tested by organizing dissemination/exploitation workshops, driven and promoting also the collaborative methodology defined in the proposal. Over the next months, PNO will moderate from two to three exploitation workshops. These workshops aim to actively engage project partners in identifying and analyzing the exploitation potential of project results and primary assets, encompassing both tangible and intangible aspects. They will serve as a platform for partners to identify and discuss primary risks associated with exploitation, validate the exploitation strategy, monitor ongoing exploitation activities, and deliberate on the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategy (to be organized together with INLECOM).

The Stakeholder Analysis was prepared within the task T5.1 on M6 and was presented in D5.1. The organization of the first Exploitation workshop will be particularly relevant in the near future. It's important to note that this document is a dynamic record continuously updated as the project progresses, with updates scheduled for M24 and M36.

2 Introduction

This document serves as the cornerstone for ReNEW exploitation strategy framework. Upcoming milestones encompass the identification of key assets, accompanied by a comprehensive synthetic description of each Key Exploitable Result (KER). The document will outline the primary steps for developing these KERs, provide background information, and present a roadmap for necessary actions. To ensure relevance to the project's unique requirements, a tailored approach will be applied to refine the content.

The Exploitation tasks are just started and will continue in the next months. The Stakeholder Analysis was prepared within the task T5.1 on M6 and was presented in D5.1. The organization of the first Exploitation workshop will be particularly relevant in the near future.

2.1 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is organized as follows:

- Chapter 3: provides the introduction of ReNEW project, its objective, and expected impacts of the project.
- Chapter 4: introduces the general methodologies and the key definitions for the Exploitation and IPR management, also showing a preview of some adopted tools.
- Chapter 5: reports on the project's exploitation plan, outlines the next steps, and provides updates on key exploitable results, with ongoing updates throughout the project.
- Chapter 6: conclusion is drawn.

3 ReNEW Project Introduction

The main objective of the [ReNEW project](#) is to **create and test innovative solutions for climate neutrality and climate resilience in the context of Inland Water Transport (IWT)**. A critical factor in the sustainability of the IWT system is the interdependence of infrastructure and the reliability, maintainability and resilience of barges/fleets. This work covers critical priorities such as sustainable infrastructure adjustments, improving the environmental sustainability and competitiveness of the ship fleet, digitalisation, integrating IWT into multimodal transport networks and ensuring the availability of a skilled workforce. The European Commission sees digitalisation in the transport sector as a key enabler of smart, sustainable solutions that can increase resilience, leading to economic, environmental and social benefits.

ReNEW will contribute to achieving following impact targets:

1. Help **sustain IWT network capacities** in inland waterways at levels not falling below 50% by improving navigability conditions and advancing resilience.
2. **Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience** to extreme weather and human-caused events while aiming to maintain network capacities to 80% levels during disruptions.
3. **Contribute to the sustainability** of the IWT systems network, promoting modal shift and supporting the EU goals for a 20% increase for inland waterways.
4. Ensure **resilience and smooth functioning** of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.
5. Increase the **use of recycled materials** within or across transport modes by at least 30% in the Ghent Living Lab.
6. **Reduce environmental impact** during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.

The ReNEW consortium comprises of leading representatives from various sectors across eleven European countries, each playing a crucial role in **supporting the transition of Inland Waterways Transport to smart, green, sustainable & climate-resilient sector**. The consortium will receive support from innovation experts (PNO) to effectively tackle market and innovation challenges while incorporating an external perspective through a comprehensive exploitation strategy and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 1 ReNEW value chain (source D5.1 Communication and dissemination plan, by Magellan)

3.1 The Project Objectives, Expected Impacts and Potential

An essential focus for IWT resilience is the enhancement of interaction between infrastructure management systems and barge operations. The integration of digitalization and automation presents opportunities for autonomous barges, including their interaction with infrastructure autonomously, offering economic advantages that could transform future IWT systems while ensuring climate-neutral and resilient services. However, the adoption of innovation within the IWT sector and the achievement of associated resilience and decarbonization objectives are more constrained by systemic challenges impacting the European IWT digital and energy transition than by technological limitations. The historical reluctance of the waterborne sector to embrace innovation and digitalization, primarily due to traditional operating methodologies among barge skippers/owners, has resulted in an aging, inefficient fleet with unreliable and environmentally damaging operations.

Addressing these challenges necessitates incentivizing innovations across the mentioned dimensions and robustly validating how and where innovation can support the transition to a sustainable, resilient, and highly efficient IWT system. In response to these identified challenges and gaps, ReNEW proposes:

- 01. Development of a decision-support framework including Resilience and Sustainability Quantification supporting the strategic planning and operational optimisation of Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT) by different stakeholder groups or communities in order to adapt to climate changes while maintaining competitiveness.

02. Introduction of **innovative infrastructure resilience and sustainability solutions** targeting rapid deployment after disruptive events to create new provisional links to other transport modes and building on autonomy developments and maturing green energy options.
03. Creation of a **Green Resilient IWT Dataspace and Digital Twin** primarily to facilitate data sharing among infrastructure monitoring systems, RIS, traffic management, emergency systems, and climate solutions.
04. Establishment of **four Living Labs** designed to showcase examples focusing on integrated inland waterway and hinterland infrastructure [Gent-urban, Douro-corridor, Netherlands–national/EU network perspectives], including a Living Lab specifically addressing inland waterway resilience.
05. Implementation of the **ReNEW Outreach and Upscale program** aimed at **maximizing impact pathways** through effective Communications Innovation management, Commercialisation and Capacity building and policy Recommendation led by the European Inland Waterways Transport Platform, industry clusters, and prominent industry innovators.

Figure 2 Implementation Objectives and Results Overview (source ReNEW Grant Agreement)

The ReNEW project aims to generate the following expected outcomes::

1. Help **sustain IWT network capacities** in inland waterways at levels not falling below 50% by improving navigability conditions and advancing resilience.
2. **Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience** to extreme weather and human-caused events while aiming to maintain network capacities to 80% levels during disruptions.
3. **Contribute to the sustainability** of the IWT systems network, promoting modal shift and supporting the EU goals for a 20% increase for inland waterways.
4. Ensure **resilience and smooth functioning** of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.
5. Increase the **use of recycled materials** within or across transport modes by at least 30% in the Ghent Living Lab.

6. Reduce environmental impact during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.

Figure 3 ReNEW's Impact Canvas (source ReNEW Grant Agreement)

Outputs generated by the project: The most relevant data & research outputs expected in ReNEW include:

- WP1: the framework to quantify sustainability and resilience will be described in detailed reports and technical and scientific publications according to the Open Science principle, and then further demonstrated upon available Data Spaces within living labs.
- WP2: design data, drawings, numerical analysis, techno-economic data
- WP3: framework architecture and core components of the smart data space on top of which digital twins will be developed, digital twin reference implementation documentation, code of the simulation libraries and models, demonstrators of the resilience and sustainability services for the Living Labs
- WP4: Real time data from multiple sources as defined in the data spaces in WP1/WP3
- WP5/WP6: Stakeholder's feedback and data, Technology and Market intelligence elaborated based on a mix of public data and interviews.

3.2 Possible Risks Associated with the Task

Within the risks associated with this task, a few significant concerns are identified concerning the Exploitation Strategy:

1. **Lack of Consensus on Exploitation Strategy:** This risk could result in misalignment, hampering the effective utilization of project outcomes, and potentially causing delays in project progress. This risk has relatively low probability and a high severity potentially causing critical outcomes. To mitigate this risk, the project aims to foster inclusive discussions among partners, employing consensus-building techniques to ensure alignment. Additionally, the project will establish a clear decision-making process to document and finalize the exploitation strategy, which will be articulated and communicated to all partners upon elaboration.
2. **Insufficient Protection of Exploitable Results:** This risk involves information leaks, potential compromise of intellectual property, and reduced market potential, leading to a loss of competitive advantage and possible legal disputes. With moderate probability and a high severity level of 4, it can potentially lead to compromised intellectual property, information leaks, and diminished market potential, resulting in a significant loss of competitive advantage. Moreover, it might escalate into legal disputes due to unauthorized use or exploitation of project outcomes by third parties, undermining the project's credibility and potential future efforts. To address this risk, the project will implement robust confidentiality measures, including the utilization of patents, Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs), and secure documentation practices. Stringent access controls and technological security measures will be established to safeguard intellectual property and sensitive project information. These protective measures will be defined and communicated to all partners upon the elaboration and announcement of the Exploitation Strategy.
3. **Underperforming Partner:** A potential risk involving delayed timelines, rated with a moderate probability level and a moderate severity, it can lead to decreased quality of work, and increased workload for other partners. To address this risk, the project has performance monitoring mechanisms with adequately timed reminders. Additionally, all consortium partners are dedicated to the project's success, allowing grace periods initially. The flexible project management structure and contractual agreement facilitate resource reallocation to alternative projects if necessary.

4 Approach to Exploitation

4.1 General definitions

The Exploitation can be considered as “the utilisation of results in further developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities”.

The primary goal of exploitation is to leverage project outcomes through scientific, economic, political, or societal channels, with the overarching aim of translating research and innovation (R&I) initiatives into tangible value and impact for society. This involves the practical application of research results, extending beyond mere commercial use. The intended recipients of these efforts include not only the project partners but also external user groups that actively incorporate the project results into their own activities.

The diverse array of products stemming from exploitation activities is illustrated in the Figure below. Each product, whether it’s a tangible item, service, patent, or other, corresponds to specific outcomes of the project and may play a key role in a particular exploitation strategy for utilizing or benefiting from the project. By thoughtfully examining the potential products arising from a project and formulating a comprehensive exploitation plan, innovators can guarantee that their efforts yield substantial real-world impact. The process of exploitation is indispensable for translating inventive ideas into tangible, meaningful results.

Figure 4 Possible products of exploitation activities

Useful Definitions:

- **“Exploitation”** means the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.
- **“Dissemination”** means the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.
- **“Commercialization”** is the process of turning products and services into a commercially viable value. Concerning Intellectual Property (IP), this term can be more specifically defined as the process of bringing IP to the market in view of future profits and business growth.
- **“Use”** is usually defined as the *direct or indirect* utilization of the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.
- **“Direct use”** implies that partners utilize the results themselves for commercial applications (e.g., by producing and/or commercializing a new product or by integrating a new process into their manufacturing plant) and/or for further research (“further” with respect to the scope of the project in which the foreground is generated).
- **“Indirect use”** implies that partners may allow third parties to exploit the research results through a

4.1.1 KER – Key Exploitable Results

By definition, a Result is [defined by the European Commission](#) as “any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected”. Thinking about the results achieved within a project, **the Key Exploitable Results are the outputs generated during the project which can be used and create impact, either by the project partners or by other stakeholders**. The project results can be reusable and exploitable (e.g., inventions, prototypes, services) as such, or elements (knowledge, technology, processes, networks) that have the potential to contribute to further work on research or innovation.

	KER Type	Expl. Route	Market
	Product	Sales / Manufacturing	
	Process	Consultancy Services	
	Know-how	Spin-off projects	
	Networking	Education	
	Data	Licensing	
			Lab

Figure 5 KER categorization (non-exhaustive list)

In ReNEW there will be a thorough assessment of the KERs innovation value. Different tools may be used to harvest the relevant data at the due time, such as the Innovation Canvas reported below. For each result the relevant issues are related to:

- The **goals/usage** foreseen
- Its **created value** (the corresponding market/users and economic potential)
- The **Partners that co-develop** during the project and the activities required
- The **necessary resources** to complete it
- The **barriers** to be overcome
- The **risks** to be faced or prevented

In general terms, these issues can be defined for each KER, regardless of being either more business or research oriented, although different terms and variables can be used (see Table 1). Once the mapping will be completed during the upcoming WorkShops, the harvested information will allow defining the exploitation route for each exploitable, its type and its closeness to market.

Table 1 KER assessment Definition guidelines

Close to Market KER assessment	More general KER assessment
Unique Value Proposition: every KER has a unique value proposition; something that differentiates it from alternative solutions or competitors.	
Customers: those who will buy/pay for your product	Users: who will use your product and gain from using it (internal or external to partners organisation).
Competitors: direct living competitors for your solution on the market or developing the same technology	Alternatives: a KER may not have direct “living” competitors, but there may be alternative solutions to the solved need: another methodology, another component, etc.
Revenue: earnings coming from an easily identifiable commercialisation strategy (e.g., sales, consultancy or licencing)	Benefits: when revenue is not the case for a KER, which may not be directly sellable as a product/service, the strategy should be identifying who pays for the cost of the resources involved (an external partner, an investor, or the budget of the company that you work for). On the other hand, the KER will have the possibility to bring a benefit (e.g., decrease costs or increase revenue of another product/service.)
Market and market size: application market segments, customers, total increase of revenue that can be gathered	Replicability potential: the total potential saving for using your product and/or the total potential investment that you can receive from external partners or your management.

by “bringing to the next stage” the solution represented by the KER.	
Commercialisation: actions needed to bring a product or service to the market and start producing revenues.	Bringing to market activities: development and implementation activities that you need to conduct before your KER is fully exploited. (e.g., lobby in the standard committee, negotiate the resources within your organization, participate in the standard committee, pay for the experts in standardization to prepare the draft of the new standard.)
Business & Financial plan: concrete forecasts of sales, project financial results and value for money, financial needs for the scale up and resources assessment	Resources needed and financial needs: identification of further steps for the KERs. Analysis of needed support, resources, public funding.

4.1.2 Exploitation Routes

Converting knowledge resulting from publicly funded research activities can be realised in various ways, including sale of technology, licencing, joint venture, spin-off, etc. The below table provides a non-exhaustive summary of potential exploitation channels / strategies for the ReNEW project results.

Table 2 Examples of Exploitation Routes

Exploitation Route	Description
Direct Sales	Direct sales of new products or services (e.g., manufacturing)
IP protection	Saving the generated IP under the form of <i>Secret Know-how, patents, copyright, trademarks</i> or designs among others. This enables keeping others from using the technology or selling licenses to do it.
Licensing	A licence agreement is a contract that grants a third party (licensee) the right to use the IP of the IP holder for a defined purpose, within the limits set by the provisions of the contract. In general, licensing will provide the IP holder with certain financial provisions. Various types of licensing are known, including exclusive (only the licensee), non-exclusive (multiple licensees) and sole (only licensee and licensor).
Consultancy	Services to solve a third party’s problem using specific knowledge or IP.

Spin-off	A spin-off refers to a separate company usually established to bring IP onto the market. It is deemed to be a valuable channel to transform the generated results into product and service, as well as to license out technology. Most importantly, <i>spin-offs are considered as a fundamental mediator between the research environment and industries</i> as they are a powerful means of technology transfer between these two sectors.
Joint Ventures/ Strategic Alliances	Joint ventures are a type of collaborative commercialisation. It is a situation where two or more parties jointly commit resources and research efforts to projects. Joint venture may <i>range from short-term projects to long-lasting strategic partnerships with multiple members and stakeholders</i> . More specifically, the parties to the joint venture share risks and contribute with their intellectual capital to technology research and development, production, marketing, and further commercialisation
Collaborative spin-off research	Commercialisation of research results through collaboration of academia with one or more industrial partners. Issues involving the ownership of IP are facilitated through contracts, covering ownership scenarios, exploitation of results and licensing rights issues.
PhD, Thesis, Training courses	A subset of new spin-off research based on the definition of new training courses, new PhD thesis and research

4.2 General Exploitation Methodology

4.2.1 Governance and Main Outline

The main methodological pillars of the ReNEW exploitation approach are a **mix of live-action interactions, desktop/intelligence studies and business research**. The core keywords for exploitation are as follows:

- **A collaborative approach:** it will be applied based on Internal workshops and exploitation meetings/seminars. The main idea is to actively involve all partners, and possibly key actors and stakeholders, external experts in the exploitation process.
- **KERs - identification:** Identify each Key Exploitable Result (KER) through a series of iterative workshops (at least two WS are planned), possibly including both online sessions and face-to-face meetings, facilitated by PNO. This process will provide a clear understanding of the represented value/benefits, potential user groups, etc of each KER.
- **IPR Management:** As a crucial component of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management framework within the ReNEW project, INLECOM oversees a comprehensive process designed to foster innovation and safeguard intellectual property. This involves

implementing a Project Outcomes registry in the form of a questionnaire to efficiently detect and nurture patentable ideas among project partners. This process includes also IPR needs and requirements for each KER. Furthermore, an IPR checklist will be prepared for each KER, detailing: (co)owners of results, IPR model, partnerships, and resources. The technology and market outlook to be realised by PNO will complement the Freedom-To-Operate analyses that each partner should perform according to their standard practices. Finally, an initial market research assessment will take place supporting the abovementioned methodological approach to identify primary target markets for any potential technologically innovative outcomes deriving from the project as well as explore any possible value propositions based on the innovation outcomes registry.

- Exploitation and Business planning:** some of the results generated will be acknowledged as key by the consortium and following the definition of ownership of KERs and related IPR agreements, Joint Exploitation Agreements (JEA) may be stipulated among two or more project partners. Negotiating additional (pre)commercial agreements with selected external stakeholders could also be part of the picture. Furthermore, additional funding sources will be explored to address future scale-up. Strategies to secure these resources will be explored, including avenues like public funding from sources such as European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), Connecting Europe Facilities (CEF), Innovation Fund (IF), LIFE Programme, and Horizon Europe IA. Additionally, consideration will be given to private funding options like investors, business angels, or crowdfunding.

In order to implement the general exploitation strategy and activities, **PNO as innovation manager will need to work closely with all partners**, especially partners including ZULU, OHB, 4SHIP, ADPL IMEC, KNT, ITA, AKKA, SF, to define and monitor the internal planning, with milestones to be met. The plan will undergo three updates during the project (M18, M24 and M36). The main exploitation activities of sHYpS, are shown in Figure below.

Significant findings from the Workshops will be used to update KERs before continuing to the next steps.

Figure 7 ReNEW overall exploitation strategy

4.2.2 Market Oriented Exploitation Route and Business Planning: Set-up

The exploitation activities will transform ReNEW technological breakthroughs into a robust business plan. This plan will include defined timelines, projected costs, and revenues. Stakeholder identification, technology outlook, and market analyses will respectively pinpoint key stakeholders and enhance understanding of the European market. Within the market outreach scope, sHYpS will engage stakeholders like shipowners, cargo owners or interested financiers in joint discussions to shape innovative demo projects.

Bringing the outside in: ReNEW will possibly engage the most interesting stakeholders based on the results of the stakeholders' analysis and consortium interest. The most interesting ones (e.g. 10) may be interviewed or engaged on a more personalized basis, including participation in workshops. The level and type of engagement can vary depending on the level of importance and interest defined for each of these stakeholders (these are also to be defined as specific results of the stakeholders' analysis).

5 ReNEW Exploitation Plan and Activities

This section is a “living” part of the document describing the more precise route and schedule for exploitation activities, with specific reference to the project Work Plan and briefly reporting about the results achieved. It will be generally structured as follows:

- Exploitation and IPR plan set-up
- Partners Exploitation plans and KERs Identification, analysis and IP management.
- Next Actions

These sections will be updated in D5.6(M24) and D5.7 (M36).

5.1 Exploitation Plan Set-up and Reporting

The overall exploitation activities in ReNEW connect the whole project, including Dissemination and Exploitation plans, Stakeholders and Market/technology Outlook, Economic analysis, Business planning, Training, IPR items Definition, Workshops and Stakeholders Events.

The exploitation plan begins by identifying KERs and defining their commercial potential. These frameworks will serve as the foundation for the overall Exploitation strategy and plan. Simultaneously, insights into technology trends and market analysis will be utilized to shape the exploitation strategy. Subsequently, PNO will organize two exploitation workshops. During these workshops, all partners will actively engage in identifying and analysing the exploitation potential of project results and main assets, both tangible and intangible. They will also identify the primary risks associated with exploitation, discuss, and validate the exploitation strategy, monitor ongoing exploitation activities, and deliberate on the IPR strategy (supported by INLECOM). Throughout this process, each KER will be meticulously described, contributing to the preparation of the business model and plan. PNO will facilitate this collaborative effort alongside the coordinator. The final outcome will be a comprehensive Exploitation Plan and a roadmap for post-project activities. This plan will integrate insights from Market Analysis, reference to a IPR management strategies elaborated by INLECOM, ownership, governance, and a Business Plan. The overall exploitation plan of ReNEW is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 8 ReNEW integrated exploitation strategy (preliminary timeline)

5.1.1 Performed Exploitation Activities and Outcomes to M18

This document covers everything that has happened up to M18. The core Exploitation tasks will start in the second half of a second year of the project, but some related activities have already been completed:

- **D5.1 - Communication and dissemination plan**, has been completed, offering a comprehensive stakeholder analysis and functional knowledge of emerging opportunities and competing solutions. D&C activities are building the right volume of connections, already giving ReNEW a good visibility and fostering community building. This document has a pivotal role in developing targeted engagement and outreach strategies.
- To offer a comprehensive overview of the ReNEW innovation ecosystem, we integrated a **gender perspective in the D6.9**, with a specific focus on women's involvement in the transport sector. A workshop was facilitated by PNO (CiaoTech) on the 6th of December 2023, and covered various topics, including discussions on gender equality, engagement of women in the transport sector, the European Commission guidelines for gender equality activities in Horizon projects, and deliberations on Gender Equality Plans.
- **The 1st Exploitation workshops schedule and content have been defined**. Some flexibility is built in, allowing customization based on the project's pace and partner proactivity. In the coming months (up to M20), the first exploitation workshop will take place online, with all partners participating. PNO will moderate the workshop together with INLECOM, collaborating

with specific partners to address their individual concerns regarding KERs and IPR. The preliminary agenda of the 1st workshop is in the Table 3. The workshop duration is about 2h. The following objectives of the workshop are:

- Refresh the fundamentals of IPR in EU funded projects
- Discuss actual KERs list among partners
- Set the basis for Business Models
- Set action points for RENEW Exploitation
- Project engagement strategy towards external stakeholders

Table 3 Preliminary agenda of the 1st workshop

AGENDA	
15 min	Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content of the exploitation workshop • IPR Management in EU funded projects (<i>presentation to the partners of the main concept, recommendations, issues on the IPR management</i>) (INLE) • ReNEW CA (INLE)
60 min	Working Groups Session (PNO: ALL) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on ReNEW KER list (PNO: ALL) • Mapping of potentially valuable and exploitable results, identifying different types of results and their potential user groups – on partner and/or consortium level (PNO+INLE: ALL) • Brainstorming on relevant information (<i>preliminary analysis of joint interests, access rights, risk analysis on each KERs -- data harvested in an Excel sheet during the workshop</i>) (PNO+INLE: ALL)
30 min	ReNEW Engagement strategy towards external stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of key stakeholders along the project value chain (PNO)
15 min	Wrap-up session

Prior to the workshop, an Excel spreadsheet listing KERs, and their characteristics (see Figure below) will be distributed to partners, who will be asked to complete the information beforehand. During the workshop, each KER will be further elaborated upon, directing attention towards potential exploitation routes, IPRs, legal or normative considerations, time to market, financial resources post-project, etc.

Exploitable output name	Exploitable output Developers
Description	Policy for Joint Ownership (if any) Access Rights (if any)
Intellectual Property (IP)	<i>What kind of protection does this project output require? (Mark in bold below or write here if different)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ Secret know how, trade secret “ Patent (<i>Invention Disclosure, patent search carried out/applied for</i>) “ Licence agreement (<i>under discussion, NDA, agreed</i>) “ Registered design “ Exclusive rights (<i>under discussion/granted</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ Trademark application “ Copyright registered “ Any other type <p><i>Notes: If the protection has already been dealt with, specify the type and the date for the IP filing.</i></p>

Figure 9 Sample of KER and their characteristics

5.2 ReNEW Key Exploitable Results

Five KERs groups have been preliminary identified at the proposal stage, as illustrated in Table 4. As the project progresses towards completion, all characteristics of each KER in terms of ownership, Technology Readiness Level (TRL), risks, exploitation routes, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) will be defined. The results of these analyses will be included in the next edition (D5.6).

Table 4 ReNEW KERs, source: ReNEW GA

KER and relevant IP items	Main owners / collaborators
WP1: a framework to quantify sustainability and resilience and a decision support system to foster their positive correlation	WP1 tasks leaders and contributors
WP2: IWT resilience and greening enhancing solutions	IPR related: ZULU, SF, OHB; Public: All
WP3: an overall architecture and core infrastructure for a data space and open digital twin for evidence-based decisions making to facilitate operators and policy makers in the development of resilient and sustainable inland waterways networks and corridors	IMEC, KNT, ITA, AKKA, and other contributors. INLE, ISL, IRTX, RDS, VLTN, ICCS, SO, 4SHIP

WP4: 4 Demonstrators	Key IP by ZULU, OHB, 4SHIP, ADPL, other contributors
WP5: scientific and policy research, market analysis	PNO, VIL, other contributors

The final exploitation report of ReNEW will be comprehensive, incorporating the Business Plan.

6 Conclusions & Future Steps

Up until M18, ReNEW has established the foundation for initiating exploitation management. Initial steps have been taken to identify stakeholders and understand market dynamics, involving communication and establishing connections with maritime stakeholders.

Given that the exploitation management strategy combines desktop analysis with live-action activities, an initial set of Exploitation Workshops has been outlined. Two Exploitation Workshops are planned, wherein all partners will participate alongside EC expert support.

In the upcoming months, the following actions are scheduled:

- Execution of the 1st exploitation workshop (planned by M20)
- Ongoing monitoring of Exploitation Actions.
- Revision and update of Stakeholder Analysis, market analysis, and technology outlook by M30.